

Physical Fitness Profile of Young Female Swimmers in Kolkata, India

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted on a group of young female swimmers in Kolkata, West Bengal. All the participants belonged to the age range 11 years to 18 years. Various physical parameters like height, weight, were measured. In addition, some fitness parameters like Body mass index (BMI), Cardiovascular fitness (VO^{2max}) were determined. All the primary data were subjected to statistical analysis after words. Calculation of mean values of all the parameters was done. Correlation study and significant study were also done thereafter. The results revealed, significant correlation between age and VO^{2max} and between BMI and VO^{2max} .

KEYWORDS: BMI, Swimmer, VO^{2max} , Fitness

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INTRODUCTION

Physical fitness is necessary for everyone. It refers to the ability of our body systems to work together efficiently to allow us to be healthy and perform activities of daily living. A fit person can respond effectively to normal situations. Physical fitness is made-up of all 11 parts- 6 of them health related and 5 skills related. All the parts are important for good performance in physical activity, including sports. Health related fitness may include cardiorespiratory endurance, muscular endurance, power, flexibility, and strength. Whereas, skill related physical fitness help us to perform well in sports and other activities that require motor skills. Such as speed help us in sports such as track and field (1).

Swimming is an individual and team racing sport, that requires the one's entire body to move through water. Archeological and the other evidence shows that, swimming has been practiced as early as 2500 BCE in Egypt and thereafter in Assyrian, Greek and Roman civilizations. In Rome and Greece swimming was a part of martial training and was also a part of elementary education in males. In the United States swimming was first nationally organized as a sport by the Amateur Athletic Union (AAU) on its foundation

in 1888. The Federation International de Natation Amateur (FINA) was founded in 1909. Internationally, competitive swimming came into prominence with its inclusion in the modern Olympic Games from their inception in 1896 (2).

In addition to these individual events, four swimmers can take part in either a freestyle or medley relay. Medley relay consist of four swimmers who can swim different strokes ordered as backstroke, breaststroke, butterfly, and freestyle.

The swimmers have some injuries. The rotator cuff in the shoulder is most susceptible to injury in swimmers. Injury to rotator cuff results from repeated trauma and overuse. Out of the four tendons in the rotator cuff, the supraspinatus is more prone to tearing. Another important is swimmer's knee. Additionally proper warm-up stretches and strength training exercises should be completed before any rigorous movements.

VO^{2max} refers to the maximum oxygen uptake during exercise and its commonly measure our aerobic endurance. Swimming can also increase our VO^{2max} which measures how efficiently our body process

oxygen, our heart moves blood to our muscles. VO^{2max} measurement is most important for distance swimmers. Hypoxic training or restrictive oxygen intake can improve VO^{2max} .

Research revealed common injury sites (shoulder, neck, back) are examined and pathologies to these areas are explained. Common spinal injury sites are Cervical spine and Lumbo pelvic complex. Managing swimming back pain includes assessing and correcting spinal and pelvic joint mobility manipulative and mobilizing techniques. However, rest and reduced training necessary for recovery (3).

In a survey of 1972 Canadian Olympic Swim team, it was reported that 12 out of 43 (28%) orthopedic consultations were for knee pain. Knee pain occurred in 70 out of these 261 swimmers or 27%, and all who reported knee pain were breaststroke swimmers.

Research describes the maximal aerobic power in competitive swimmers by performing a pulling exercise with elastic shock cords and a treadmill run to exhaustion. The mean $vo2max$ is significantly higher in swimmers in pulling test ($p < 0.01$). The maximum heart rates achieved pulling were 96% by swimmers. The swimmers reach about 79% of their running VO^{2max} by pulling (4).

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the present study were:

- To determine the VO^{2max} of female swimmers
- To observe the BMI status of the female swimmers
- To find out the common injury sites of the female swimmers
- To observe the VO^{2max} of girls of 11-18 years swimmers

METHODOLOGY

The cross-sectional study was done and data were collected from several renowned swimming clubs in Kolkata, West Bengal

Sampling

The stratified clustered sampling technique was applied for the selection of swimmers. There were all together twenty young female swimmers (age 11yrs - 18yrs) participated as human subject for the study. All participants were the resident of the district of Kolkata, West Bengal.

Study Design

The present study was conducted by giving the writing consent to the authority of the swimming academy and by taking the verbal consent from the swimmers. The entire study was done in 3phases. i.e.; pre & post exercise states. In the first phase (pre-exercise state) data of the physical parameters like height, weight etc. was collected. In the second phase, the collection of data regarding injuries related to swimming (questionnaire) was done. In the third phase, the physiological parameter like resting heart rate, VO^{2max} value were taken applying standard procedure. The same protocol was followed for the post-exercise states.

Inclusion Criteria

- Regular female swimmers were included in this study.
- Swimmers without any present injury were selected.
- Age group of 11yrs to 18 yrs were only considered.

Exclusion Criteria

- Male swimmers were not considered.
- No sedentary people have been taken for the study.
- Currently injured swimmers were not selected

Test Methods:

The data of physical parameters like height, weight was collected by standardized methods (5). The Queens College Step Test was done to determine maximum oxygen consumption capacity (VO^{2max}). BMI (Body Mass Index) was calculated by the standard formula. following equation (6).

Statistical Analysis

All primary data were subjected to statistical treatment for result analysis. Mean & SD were calculated. After that mean scores were subjected to significance test by applying student t-test. Significance level was set at 0.05.

NULL HYPOTHESIS OF T-TEST (No) – There is no significant effect of VO^{2max} on swimmers according to their age. Condition of the acceptance of null hypothesis is the critical t value $>$ calculated t value.

RESULT

Table- 1: Represents the basic details of the Female Swimmers. The basic details like Name, Age, Sex, Height and Weight of the participants. After Table- 1 in the following tables the participants have been shown by their serial no. instead of their names.

Serial No.	Age	Sex	Body Height (cm)	Body Weight (kg)
1	11	Female	147.32	34
2	12	Female	154.94	42
3	12	Female	147.32	42
4	12	Female	154.94	39
5	13	Female	152.4	43
6	13	Female	160.02	53
7	13	Female	160.02	52.6
8	13	Female	157.48	41.5
9	14	Female	157.48	54
10	14	Female	155.5	49
11	15	Female	170.18	60
12	15	Female	154.94	42
13	16	Female	162.56	50
14	16	Female	154.94	58
15	16	Female	162.56	61
16	17	Female	157.48	52
17	18	Female	170.18	63
18	18	Female	163.56	54
19	18	Female	167.64	62
20	18	Female	165.1	61
Mean	14.7		158.828	50.655

Table- 2: Represents the data of BMI (Body Mass Index) and Maximum oxygen consumption (Vo2 max). According to the BMI we can interpret that who is underweight, normal weight or obese athlete. Whereas with the help of value obtained from Vo2max, we can interpret the fitness profile or maximum oxygen consumption of the athletes. Most of the swimmers have normal weight and few have underweight. With age the vo2max level increases.

Serial Number	BMI (kg/m ²)	Age(years)	VO ² max (ml/kg/min)
1	15.7	11	39.96
2	17.7	12	41.8
3	19.44	12	40.88
4	16.45	12	39.22
5	18.6	13	40.7
6	20.7	13	42.17
7	20.54	13	43.65
8	16.86	13	40.88
9	21.95	14	42.17
10	20.41	14	39.96
11	20.26	15	40.7
12	17.7	15	41.8
13	19	16	43.65
14	24.47	16	41.43
15	23.28	16	42.54
16	21.1	17	45.5
17	21.79	18	44.57
18	20.37	18	44.39
19	22.3	18	45.13
20	22.42	18	45.5
	20.052	14.7	42.33

Table- 3: Represents the correlation between age & VO^{2max} and BMI & VO^{2max} . Depending upon the value of the r we state the Age shows significant correlation with the VO^{2max} .

There is also a correlation present between BMI and Vo2max but the level of significance is low. The t value of age and vo2max significant at 0.001 level whereas, and the t value of BMI and vo2max is significant at 0.02 level.

Age(years)	VO^{2max} ml/kg/min)	SL. No	BMI (Body Mass Index)	VO^{2max} ml/kg/min)
11	39.96	1	15.7	39.96
12	41.8	2	17.7	41.8
12	40.88	3	19.44	40.88
12	39.22	4	16.45	39.22
13	40.7	5	18.6	40.7
13	42.17	6	20.7	42.17
13	43.65	7	20.54	43.65
13	40.88	8	16.86	40.88
14	42.17	9	21.95	42.17
14	39.96	10	20.41	39.96
15	40.7	11	20.26	40.7
15	41.8	12	17.7	41.8
16	43.65	13	19	43.65
16	41.43	14	24.47	41.43
16	42.54	15	23.28	42.54
17	45.5	16	21.1	45.5
18	44.57	17	21.79	44.57
18	44.39	18	20.37	44.39
18	45.13	19	22.3	45.13
18	45.5	20	22.42	45.5

Correlation of Age with VO^{2max} :0.80 Correlation of BMI with VO^{2max} :0.54

P value between age and VO^{2max} = 0.003

Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected as there is a significant effect of age on VO^{2max}

DISCUSSION

The findings of this present study that look out female swimmers BMI and VO^{2max} . Table 2 and 3 shows the physical and physiological parameters. Table 4 shows the correlation between BMI and VO^{2max} in regards to age (7,8). Where vo^{2max} has a higher level of significance with age and BMI has a comparatively lower level of significance with age. In table 5 the statistical analysis showing significant difference of VO^{2max} between two age groups ($p < 0.05$). The t-test value represents the comparison of average vo2max level between 11-14years girls and 15-18years girl's swimmers (9). The result shows that, older athletes have greater VO^{2max} than the younger one. A high level of vo2max indicates a high level of fitness. It makes sense that a high level of fitness means improved endurance, which increases cardiovascular performance that efficiently transport oxygen in the body, and better overall performance (10). The extra oxygen in the blood allows to provide good swimming economy. By lowering the resting heart rate (HR) and the HR at submaximal loads, the heart pumps more blood with every heartbeat (11). This in

addition to the other physiological changes, increases the oxygen extraction capacity. Like adding increased miles per gallon to the engine of a car, VO^{2max} increases the distance a swimmer can go without tiring (12). Top endurance swimmers all have higher than normal VO^{2max} level. The regular practice of swimming increases core strength. On the other hand, the obese or overweight girls had lower relative VO^{2max} than the reference group. With increase age obese children were found to be at a risk of physical inactivity both at school and in leisure time. Organized physical activity in leisure time influenced relative VO^{2max} but the variance was primarily experienced by BMI. The relative VO^{2max} x is inversely proportional to fat mass – that is the more body fat someone have, the lower will be their level of vo2max. In fact, fat mass is a better predictor of relative vo2max than exercise performance. In table 6 the graphical representation shows that, at 11-14years age the VO^{2max} is lower than mean level whereas, at 15-18years age group the mean vo2max is higher than the level of mean. It shows that with age the swimmers develop more endurance as a result the

level of VO_2^{max} is high which helps them in better performance (13).

Future Aspects of the Study:

In present study due to time constrain some more relative factors like dietary health and mental health conditions of the players could not be studied. However, in future a more comprehensive study plan will be discussed

CONCLUSION

As lower age group of 11-14years old girl swimmers had lower level of VO_2^{max} than the upper age 15-18years old swimmers, so as far for the improvement of their VO_2^{max} level they need to go through the HIIT training. It is the fastest way to improve their level of VO_2^{max} quickly. The key success of HIIT is to vary the intensity and duration of the training. They can introduce more endurance training in their schedule, such as walking, jogging, running etc. On the other hand, as obese children had lower VO_2^{max} level so they need to work out more for a more effective result in their performance.

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